

SCHOOL HEADS' INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES AND PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the level of instructional leadership competencies and practices and the instructional leadership practices of the school heads in SDO Camarines Norte. A quantitative method using descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 294 school heads from both public elementary and secondary schools. These respondents were selected through total enumeration sampling, as all identified school heads within the study area were invited to participate regardless of their position included Principals, Head Teachers, and Teachers-in-Charge of the public schools in the Division of Camarines Norte. Data were obtained using researcher-made instrument and analyzed using weighted mean and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r). The findings revealed that the level of instructional leadership competencies of school heads with an overall weighted mean of 3.64 all interpreted as Highly Competent (HC). The instructional leadership practices with an overall weighted mean of 3.77 interpreted as Always Practiced (AP). There was a significant relationship between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads, all correlation coefficients (r) are positive and significant at $p=.000$. The study proposed an Instructional Leadership Capacity Enhancement Plan to enhance the instructional competencies and practices of the school heads.

Keywords: *Instructional competencies, instructional leadership, teaching standards and pedagogies, teacher performance feedback, learner achievement and other performance indicators, learning assessment, learning environment and learner discipline*

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamically shifting field of education, the function of instructional leadership has attained significant importance, emerging as a decisive element in the improvement of teaching methodologies and student learning results. Instructional leaders, typically school principals, are tasked with fostering a school environment that promotes effective instructional practices, thereby directly impacting student achievement. The efficacy of curriculum implementation and the successful delivery of instruction are profoundly dependent upon the operational functions of school heads (He, et al. 2024).

Several foundational laws and policies outline the demanding and multi-faceted role of school heads in the Philippines. The Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 (RA 9155) defines the school head as both an administrator and an instructional leader, while the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (RA 10533) mandates that these leaders receive continuous training in academic, administrative, and community leadership. To standardize and promote continuous professional growth (career-long learning), the DepEd issued the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) (DepEd Order No. 024, s. 2020) and restructured the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP), (DepEd Order No. 011, s. 2019).

Research Questions

1. What is the level of Instructional leadership competencies of school head in terms of
 - 1.1 teaching standards and pedagogies
 - 1.2 teacher performance feedback
 - 1.3 Learner achievement and other performance indicators
 - 1.4 learning assessment
 - 1.5 learning environment and
 - 1.6 learner discipline?
2. What are the instructional leadership practices of the school heads along the aforementioned variables?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents along instructional leadership competencies and practices?
5. What intervention may be proposed to enhance the instructional leadership competencies and practices of school heads?

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative method using a descriptive-correlational design was employed to determine the level of instructional leadership competencies and practices, and the instructional leadership practices, as well as the challenges encountered by school heads of SDO, Camarines Norte. The study employed total enumeration sampling, wherein all

323 schools heads were included and invited to participate, however, only 294 school heads successfully responded, the remaining 29 were unable to participate due to some reasons.

Data were gathered using researcher-made survey questionnaire covering level of Instructional leadership competencies and practices, and instructional leadership practices of the school heads. Five experts was invited to validate the questionnaire. After the validation, researcher conducted a pilot testing to 20 Department Heads who were not part of the study. Using cronbach-alpha, the results along instructional leadership competencies, higher than 0.80 that suggest high reliability, while instructional leadership practices, result is higher than 0.80 with good consistency.

Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics v21. Weighted mean was employed along level of instructional leadership competencies, and instructional leadership practices. It also employed to determine the challenges encountered by the respondents along instructional leadership competencies and practices. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized to determined significant relationship between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads.

RESULTS

This part presents the study's findings relevant to the level of instructional leadership competencies and practices of school heads of SDO Camarines Norte along with teaching standards and pedagogies, teacher performance feedback, learner achievement and other performance indicators, learning assessment, learning environment, and learning discipline. Additionally, it examined the significant relationship between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads. Further, it determined the challenges encountered by the respondents along instructional leadership competencies and practices. The insights gained from this analysis served as the foundation for developing intervention tailored to enhance the instructional leadership competencies and practices of school heads.

Level of Instructional Leadership Competencies of School Heads

Teaching Standards and Pedagogies. The findings indicate that the level of school heads of the instructional leadership competencies in teaching standards and pedagogies were the central components of instructional leadership competencies. The two highest -rated indicator (3.70) highlights assess teaching practices and provide constructive feedback for improvement. However, aware of various pedagogies and encourage teachers in the adoption in the classroom, rated lowest at 3.62, but still interpreted as highly competent. With an overall weighted mean 3.68, interpreted as "Highly Competent (HC)," the data confirmed that they practically have sufficient knowledge of curriculum provisions and alignment, effective pedagogies and teaching

strategies and evidence-based practices that directly reinforce quality education and instruction.

Table 1
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Teaching Standards and Pedagogies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand and implement National Curriculum Framework in the school	3.69	HC
2. Know the content, skills, and values embedded in the curriculum	3.67	HC
3. Discuss curriculum updates with teachers	3.69	HC
4. Promote effective teaching practices	3.69	HC
5. Aware of various pedagogies and encourage teachers in the adoption in the classroom	3.62	HC
6. Identify areas where teachers need support	3.65	HC
7. Provide professional development for teachers	3.68	HC
8. Assess teaching practices	3.70	HC
9. Provide constructive feedback for improvement	3.70	HC
10. Fulfill responsibilities related to instructional leadership	3.69	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.68	HC
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Highly Competent (HC)	
2.50-3.24 -	Competent (C)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Moderately Competent (MC)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Competent (NC)	

Teacher Performance Feedback. The findings show that the level of school heads aware of legal and ethical considerations when providing feedback, as reflected in the highest-rated indicator (3.71). However, the lowest-rated indicator (3.53) highlights providing regular and consistent feedback to teachers. With an overall weighted mean of 3.64, interpreted as “ Highly Competent (HC)”. The study suggest that consistent feedback enables the teachers to understand expectations, refine instructional quality and foster sustainable professional development. Also, they believed that well-recognized teachers result to better pedagogical and well-recognized teachers result to better pedagogical and professional development and effectiveness.

Table 2
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Teacher Performance Feedback

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Provide feedback that is based on data and evidence	3.63	HC

2. Provide regular and consistent feedback to teachers	3.53	HC
3. Provide feedback that is specific, clear, and actionable	3.61	HC
4. Encourage a two-way communication process during feedback sessions	3.70	HC
5. Work with teachers to set professional growth goals	3.66	HC
6. Culturally sensitive when providing feedback	3.64	HC
7. Ensure that feedback sessions are Confidential	3.68	HC
8. Aware of legal and ethical considerations when providing feedback	3.71	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.64	HC

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:
3.25-4.00 -	Highly Competent (HC)
2.50-3.24 -	Competent (C)
1.75- 2.49 -	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.00-1.74 -	Not Competent (NC)

Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators. The findings indicate that foster a culture of accountability within the school, where data-driven decisions are valued and used to continuously improve outcomes for all learners, with the highest-rated indicator (3.67) highlights that teachers, staff and learners take shared responsibility for enhancing teaching and learning outcomes. However, the lowest-rated indicator (3.56), which highlights the track learners' progress and measure impact. This indicates skills enable them to create informed, data-oriented decisions that directly enhance teaching and learning. With an overall weighted mean of 3.62 interpreted as “ Highly Competent (HC)”.

Table 3
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Define and explain various achievement indicators (e.g., passing rate, completion rate, etc)	3.66	HC
2. Identify learners' areas for improvement	3.64	HC
3. Guide teachers in adjusting their teaching strategies and materials to better meet learners' needs	3.64	HC
4. Track learners' progress and measure impact	3.56	HC
5. Use data to justify requests for additional resources such as teacher training or learning materials	3.57	HC

6. Foster a culture of accountability within the school, where data-driven decisions are valued and used to continuously improve outcomes for all learners	3.67	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.62	HC
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Highly Competent (HC)	
2.50-3.24 -	Competent (C)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Moderately Competent (MC)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Competent (NC)	

Learning Assessment. The findings indicate show that school heads along learning assessment ensuring adherence to national assessment policies and guidelines were the highest-rated indicator 3.65 interpreted as highly competent. The policies offer standardized, fair and valid framework for evaluating learner’s achievements and school performance. However, need to enhance their capacity to evaluate assessment tools by teachers in the school, rated lowest at 3.52. With an overall weighted mean of 3.58 interpreted as “Highly Competent (HC)”.

Table 4
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Learning Assessment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand assessment principles to better support the teachers in designing effective learning assessment	3.58	HC
2. Familiar with the purpose of different assessment tools and techniques	3.58	HC
3. Knowledge of the national assessment framework and policies	3.56	HC
4. Capacity to evaluate assessment tools used by teachers in the school	3.52	HC
5. Ensure the school adhere to national assessment policies and guidelines	3.65	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.58	HC
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Highly Competent (HC)	
2.50-3.24 -	Competent (C)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Moderately Competent (MC)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Competent (NC)	

Learning Environment. The findings indicate that level of school heads of instructional leadership along learning environment, a positive and supportive learning environment promotes learner engagement, safety, motivation and well- being. The highest-rated indicator (3.83) highlights showing respect to everyone at all times and

providing gender-fair learning opportunities. However, school heads must ensure that teachers work according to the schools' education goals, rated lowest at 3.71, presents they practically communicate a shared vision and regularly adapt teaching practices with that vision. With an overall weighted mean of 3.77, interpreted as "Highly Competent (HC)". the data confirmed that they purposefully design learning conditions that support teaching effectiveness and positive learning outcomes. purposive, nurturing and supportive to learners' development.

Table 5
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Learning Environment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Show respect to everyone at all times	3.83	HC
2. Provide gender-fair learning opportunities	3.83	HC
3. Uphold gender sensitivity in dealing with learners	3.80	HC
4. Recognize that every learner has strength	3.77	HC
5. Maintain learning environment that promotes courtesy and respect for all learners	3.77	HC
6. Create a student-centered environment, both in the classrooms and overall school site	3.76	HC
7. Develop discipline among the staff and students	3.72	HC
8. Ensure that teachers work according to the school' s educational goals	3.71	HC
9. Put student learning at the core of activities and decisions	3.73	HC
10. Ensure that students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive and motivating environment	3.74	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	HC
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Highly Competent (HC)	
2.50-3.24 -	Competent (C)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Moderately Competent (MC)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Competent (NC)	

Learner discipline. The finding indicate that the school heads along learning discipline guiding learners to develop self-control, responsibility, and positive behavior. The highest-rated indicator (3.72) establishing clear expectations, promoting respect, and creating a culture where students feel safe, values, and motivated to learn. However, need to improve their understanding and effectively implement school disciplinary policies, foster internal motivation amongst learners, and encourage them to take responsibility for their actions and become self-regulated individuals, suggesting school

heads can ensure that rules and policies are applied uniformly, minimizing confusion and conflicts among learners and staff. With an overall weighted mean of 3.64 interpreted as “Highly Competent (HC)”.

Table 6
Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of the School Heads along Learner Discipline

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Establish clear expectations, promote respect, and create a culture where students feel safe, values, and motivated to learn	3.72	HC
2. Prevent disruptive behavior of learners in school	3.64	HC
3. Understand and effectively implement school disciplinary policies	3.62	HC
4. Foster internal motivation amongst learners	3.62	HC
5. Encourage them to take responsibility for their actions and become self-regulated individuals	3.62	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	3.64	HC

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:
3.25-4.00	-Highly Competent (HC)
2.50-3.24	-Competent (C)
1.75- 2.49	-Moderately Competent (MC)
1.00-1.74	-Not Competent (NC)

Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads

Teaching Standards and Pedagogies. The findings show that the school heads of instructional leadership practices along teaching standards and pedagogies promoting high teaching standards and effective, learner-centered pedagogies, school heads ensure quality instruction, support teacher professional growth, and enhance learner achievement and overall school performance. The highest-rated indicator (3.76) highlights creating a conducive learning environment that promote student engagement and well-being, guiding teachers in using assessment data. However, school heads need to promote the use of diverse and appropriate instructional strategies, rated lowest at 3.69 interpreted as always practiced. With an overall weighted mean of 3.73, interpreted as “Always Practiced (AP),”

Table 7
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads along Teaching Standards and Pedagogies

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Demonstrate understanding of curriculum standards and guide teachers in planning effective instruction	3.73	AP

2. Provide clear guidance on curriculum alignment	3.73	AP
3. Monitor the implementation of the curriculum and instructional programs	3.70	AP
4. Promote the use of diverse and appropriate instructional strategies	3.69	AP
5. Promote student-centered learning approaches	3.73	AP
6. Create a conducive learning environment that promote student engagement and well-being	3.76	AP
7. Foster a positive classroom climate	3.74	AP
8. Guide teachers in using assessment data to improve instruction and student learning	3.76	AP
9. Ensure that assessment methods are aligned with learning objectives.	3.73	AP
10. Provide opportunities for teachers to engage in professional growth and development activities	3.76	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.73	AP
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)	
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)	

Teacher Performance Feedback. The findings indicate that school heads along teacher performance feedback is a key component of school heads’ instructional leadership practices. The highest-rated indicator (3.78) highlights the three indicators school heads focus on teachers’ strengths and areas for improvement and avoid making personal attacks or negative attacks or negative comments, respect the teachers’ privacy and avoid sharing their feedback with others, and follow school policies and procedures, and avoid discrimination or unprofessional behavior. School heads concentrate on the strengths and improve the overall teaching quality, ensuring feedback is constructive and oriented towards performance rather than personal attributes. However, consider the teacher’s background, experiences, beliefs, and avoid making assumptions or stereotypes, rated lowest at 3.69, presents these aspects significantly influence how teachers’ approach teaching delivery, instruction, interaction with learners and address pedagogical and instructional challenges. With an overall weighted mean of 3.75, interpreted as ‘Always Practiced’.

Table 8
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads
along Teacher Performance Feedback

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Use assessment results, classroom observations, and other relevant data to inform their feedback	3.76	AP
2. Provide feedback in the form of formal evaluations, informal conversations, or coaching sessions	3.77	AP
3. Focus on teacher ' s strengths and areas for improvement and avoid making personal attacks or negative comments.	3.78	AP
4. Listen to the teacher ' s perspectives, answer their questions, and provide support as needed	3.75	AP
5. Provide guidance and resources to help teachers achieve goals, and monitor their progress over time	3.73	AP
6. Consider the teacher ' s background, experiences, beliefs, and avoid making assumptions or stereotypes	3.69	AP
7. Respect the teacher ' s privacy and avoid sharing their feedback with others	3.78	AP
8. Follow school policies and procedures, and avoid discrimination or unprofessional behavior	3.78	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.75	AP

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)

Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators. The findings indicate that school heads instructional leadership practices closely linked through clear academic direction, effective supervision, data-driven decision-making, and support for quality teaching, school heads influence learners' academic outcomes, teacher performance, school climate, and overall institutional effectiveness. The highest-rated indicator (3.77) highlights monitoring the progress of the learners. However, fostering a culture of high-quality instruction, informed by learner performance data, rated lowest at 3.70, but still interpreted always practiced. With an overall weighted mean 3.73 interpreted as " Always Practiced (AP).

Table 9
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads along Learner Achievement and Other Performance Indicators

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Use achievement data to improve instructional practices, resource allocation, and school improvement planning	3.73	AP
2. Identify specific subjects, grade levels, or learner groups that may require additional support or interventions.	3.72	AP
3. Evaluate the effectiveness of implemented programs and initiatives	3.73	AP
4. Monitor the progress of the learners	3.77	AP
5. Advocate for resources and community partnership to support learners	3.74	AP
6. Foster a culture of high-quality instruction, informed by learner performance data	3.70	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.73	AP
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)	
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)	

Learning Assessment. The findings show that school heads place the learning assessment by guiding use of assessment data, ensuring alignment with learning standards, and promoting fair and meaningful evaluation. The highest-rated indicator (3.80) highlights guiding teachers in using assessment data to adjust instructional strategies and enhance learners' outcomes. However, assisting the teachers to use various assessment types (formative, summative, and diagnostic), rated lowest at 3.70, presents school heads provide support to teachers in terms of assessment by organizing trainings and workshop, initiating collaborative planning and sharing of best practices, providing assessment tools and resources and offering constructive feedback to educators based on classroom observations. With an overall weighted mean of 3.73, interpreted as " Always Practice(AP).

Table 10
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads along Learning Assessment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Assist the teachers to use various assessment types (formative, summative, and diagnostic)	3.70	AP
2. Utilize assessment data to identify school-wide strengths and weaknesses	3.73	AP

3. Encourage teachers to use assessment results to personalize learning	3.73	AP
4. Guide teachers in using assessment data to adjust instructional strategies and enhance learners' outcomes	3.80	AP
5. Facilitate discussion among teachers on assessment results and implications	3.73	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.73	AP
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)	
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)	

Learning Environment. The findings indicate school heads fostering safe, supportive, and well-organized classrooms, and promoting positive teacher-learner interactions. The highest-rated indicator (3.82) highlights maintaining a safe and orderly classroom free from distractions. However, conducting challenging learning activities despite physical rated lowest at 3.73, presents an area for improvement, suggesting the need to create an educational environment where learners are encouraged and inspired to learn independently and take accountability of their own learning. With an over all weighted mean of 3.77, interpreted as “ Always Practiced (AP).

Table 11
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads
along Learning Environment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Maintain a safe and orderly classrooms free from distractions	3.82	AP
2. Ensure safe, clean and functional school facilities	3.80	AP
3. Foster an environment where staff increase their self-awareness and learn more about their own biases, fears, and comfort levels	3.76	AP
4. Support ongoing classroom structures for diverse students	3.75	AP
5. Create stress-free environment	3.75	AP
6. Communicate and maintain high standards of learning performance	3.78	AP
7. Use individual and cooperative learning activities to improve capacities of learners for higher learning	3.77	AP
8. Foster learning in co-curricular activities and other arenas outside the classroom	3.75	AP
9. Conduct challenging learning activities despite physical	3.73	AP

10. Foster a positive school culture and climate that values diversity, inclusivity, and mutual respect	3.77	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	AP
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)	
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)	

Learner discipline. The findings show that school heads place a high priority on resolving conflicts fairly and constructively, as reflected in the highest-rated indicator (3.81) about establishing clear behavioral expectations, promoting self- discipline, and creating a respectful and orderly learning environment. However, the lowest-rated indicator (3.71) highlights minimize distractions allowing learners to focus on their studies and ultimately achieve their academic potential. With an overall weighted mean of 3.77, interpreted as “ Always Practiced (AP).

Table 12
Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads
along Learner Discipline

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Provide clear guideline and support empowers teachers to manage their classrooms effectively	3.77	AP
2. Minimize distractions allowing learners to focus on their studies and ultimately achieve their academic potential	3.71	AP
3. Ensure fair and equitable treatment	3.79	AP
4. Resolve conflicts fairly and constructively	3.81	AP
5. Provide adequate support and resources for teachers to manage classroom behavior	3.77	AP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	AP
Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:	
3.25-4.00 -	Always Practiced (AP)	
2.50-3.24 -	Moderately Practiced (MP)	
1.75- 2.49 -	Seldom Practiced (SP)	
1.00-1.74 -	Not Practiced (NP)	

Relationship Between the Instructional Leadership Competencies and Practices of the School Heads.The test for significant relationship that may exist between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads along teaching standards and pedagogies, teacher performance feedback, learner achievement and other performance indicators, learning assessment, learning environment, and learner discipline were computed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients (r). The results revealed all correlation coefficients (r) are positive and significant at $p = .000$, indicating statistically significant relationships across all

dimensions. It can be noted that the highest correlations appear between teaching standards and pedagogies with $r=.670$ to $.684$ indicating strong relationship. Teacher performance feedback with $r=.579$ to $.657$ indicating moderate to strong relationship. Lower, yet still significant relationships include learner discipline with $r=.444$ to $.587$ suggesting a moderate relationship across all variables. Learning assessment and learning environment with $r=.418$ to $.568$, also indicating moderate relationship.

Table 13
Test for Significant Relationship Between Instructional Competence and Practices of the School Heads

Instructional Practices	Instructional Competence											
	Teaching Standards and Pedagogies		Teacher Performance Feedback		Learner Achievement and other Performance Indicators		Learning Assessment		Learning Environment		Learner Discipline	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Teaching Standards and Pedagogies	.670**	.000	.684**	.000	.661**	.000	.652**	.000	.611**	.000	.637**	.000
Teacher Performance Feedback	.579**	.000	.657**	.000	.601**	.000	.620**	.000	.611**	.000	.623**	.000
Learner Achievement and other Performance Indicators	.587**	.000	.613**	.000	.574**	.000	.588**	.000	.524**	.000	.533**	.000
Learning Assessment	.520**	.000	.570**	.000	.471**	.000	.539**	.000	.490**	.000	.554**	.000
Learning Environment	.552**	.000	.544**	.000	.418**	.000	.452**	.000	.568**	.000	.587**	.000
Learner Discipline	.444**	.000	.502**	.000	.446**	.000	.462**	.000	.551**	.000	.587**	.000

**Correlation is Significant @ 0.01

*Correlation is Significant @ 0.05

Challenges Encountered by the Respondents along Instructional Leadership Competencies and Practices. The top three challenges encountered by the respondents along instructional leadership competencies and practices were constantly evolving nature of the field of education with a weighted mean of 3.59, interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA), providing meaningful and timely feedback to teachers and offering targeted coaching and support with a weighted mean of 3.44 interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA), which highlights the time, expertise, and sustained effort required to effectively mentor teachers and managing a diverse faculty with varying levels of experience, skills, and professional development needs with a weighted mean of 3.42, Strongly Agree (SA) further emphasizes the complexity of instructional leadership.

Table 14
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents along Instructional Leadership Competencies and Practices

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. School heads often find themselves overwhelmed with administrative duties, leaving little time for observing classes, coaching teachers, or analyzing student data	3.31	SA
2. Opportunities for school heads to develop their own instructional leadership skills are often scarce, hindering their ability to support teachers effectively	3.07	A
3. Limited funds can restrict access to professional learning opportunities for teachers, innovative teaching materials, and technology that can enhance instruction	3.33	SA
4. Introducing new teaching methodologies or assessment practices can meet with resistance from established teachers, requiring skillful change management	3.32	SA
5. Aligning all stakeholders, teachers, parents, and learners, around a clear vision for instructional improvement can be difficult, requiring open communication and collaboration	3.29	SA
6. Translating research-based practices into classroom realities can be challenging, requiring sustained effort and ongoing monitoring	3.30	SA
7. Managing a diverse faculty with varying levels of experience, skills, and professional development needs	3.42	SA
8. Providing teachers with meaningful and timely feedback on their practice, and offering targeted coaching and support, takes time and expertise	3.44	SA
9. School heads may lack the skills needed to effectively analyze learner performance data to identify trends, gaps, and areas for improvement	2.94	A
10. The field of education is constantly evolving, requiring school heads to keep abreast of new research, best practices, and emerging technologies	3.59	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.30	SA

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:
3.25-4.00 -	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50-3.24 -	Agree (A)
1.75- 2.49 -	Disagree (D)
1.00-1.74 -	Strongly Disagree (SD)

DISCUSSION

A “Highly Competent (HC)” over all rating for the level of instructional leadership competencies and practices of the school heads indicates that school leaders demonstrate strong capability in guiding teaching and learning processes within the school. Their ability to guide teaching practices, support teacher development, monitor learner progress, implement meaningful assessments and maintain a positive learning environment contributes significantly to the overall quality of education in the school. These competencies strengthen the teaching-learning process and support the achievement of institutional goals and improved student outcomes. These findings aligned with studies by Flores and Dopeno (2024) who also found that the leadership practices of school heads in collaborative approach were viewed as one of the salient determinants of the conducive learning environment and system that benefit learners’ performance and achievements. It was also concluded that the school heads set highest priorities on enhancing the educational support for the learners as learners’ achievement belongs to the major indicators of school development and success. Also, Mirana (2022) conformed that the learning outcomes positively associated with the learning environment. Moreover, classroom learning dimensions are good indicators of teaching and learning process. These dimensions have been used to predict student learning outcomes and the possibility of enhancing those outcomes by changing the classroom environment.

Although, the results showing that the instructional leadership practices of school heads were reflect the commitment of school heads to consistently carry out their instructional leadership roles. Their regular engagement in guiding teaching practices, supporting teacher development, monitoring student performance, implementing effective assessments strategies, and maintaining a positive learning environment contributes to the overall improvement of school performance. This consistency in leadership practices strengthens the teaching-learning process and support the achievement of educational goals. These findings align with Dimatera (2024) , who emphasized the instructional leadership of school administrators posed direct impacts on the educational environment and system guiding learners’ discipline for the learners and the quality of support systems for both learners and educators. It was also concluded that the instructional leadership of school heads positively impact the learning system, discipline, behavioral management and environment by offering guidance to teachers’ practices and ensuring a concentrated and structured learning atmosphere guided by relevant educational and socially-oriented goals. Similarly, as stated in the study of Lescano (2021) who emphasized that the instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, parents’ involvement and community partnership and research management posted impact to the leadership performance of the school.

The significant relationship between instructional leadership competencies and practices reveled that as instructional practices improve, so does instructional competence, highlighting a strong alignment between what school heads do (practices) and what they know and can apply (competence). The result was conformed by Jimenez and Galicia (2023) which revealed that there is a significant relationship between the school head’s level of instructional leadership skills/practices and their level of their

competencies. Similarly, as stated in the study of Daing et al. (2023), there is a significant relationship between the school administrators' overall instructional leadership skills and the teachers' performance.

This implies that school heads feel considerable pressure to continuously update their knowledge and adapt to new research, emerging technologies, and changing policies. This finding may be attributed to the continuous implementations of initiatives and innovations introduced in schools. School heads are often required to implement new curriculum standards and integrate emerging technologies, sometimes all at the same time. Before guiding teachers, they must first thoroughly understand these changes themselves through trainings, policy reviews, and professional learning activities. They are then expected to lead orientations, monitor implementation, and address challenges that arise in classrooms. Because new directives and advancements are frequently introduced, school heads experience ongoing pressure to adapt and remain informed. The findings align with Lincuna and Caingcoy (2020), who highlighted school heads have faced difficulties dealing with teachers' attitudes, competing schedules and activities, and instructors' resistance to change.

Conclusions

School heads demonstrate a strong level of instructional leadership in both competence and practice. Their instructional leadership competencies were rated as Highly Competent across all domains, including teaching standards and pedagogies, teacher performance feedback, learner achievement and other performance indicators, learning assessment, learning environment, and learner discipline. Among these, learning environment obtained the highest rating, indicating strength in creating supportive and effective learning conditions. The instructional leadership practices of the school heads were assessed as Always Practiced in all areas. This suggests that school heads consistently apply leadership behaviors related to teaching standards and pedagogies, teacher performance feedback, learner achievement and other performance indicators, learning assessment, learning environment, and learner discipline.

The results show a statistically significant positive relationship between the instructional leadership competencies and practices of school heads across all dimensions ($p = .000$). Strong correlations were found in teaching standards and pedagogies, while teacher performance feedback showed moderate to strong relationships. Learner discipline, learning assessment, and learning environment demonstrated moderate yet significant correlations. These findings indicate that improved instructional practices are associated with higher instructional competence. The findings also indicate that school heads strongly agree that the constantly evolving nature of education, the demand for meaningful and timely teacher feedback and coaching, and the challenge of managing a diverse faculty are the primary difficulties in instructional leadership. These challenges highlight the complexity and dynamic demands of their role. In response, a targeted Instructional Leadership Capacity Enhancement Plan is proposed to enhance school heads' capacity to adapt to educational changes, provide effective teacher support, and manage diverse teaching personnel efficiently.

Recommendations

The School Division Office may implement ongoing professional development for school heads, focusing on areas with lower scores such as learning assessment and learner achievement. Regular bench marking, peer collaboration, and advanced leadership training may help sustain and enhance instructional leadership competencies across all domains.

School heads may receive ongoing professional development focused on adapting to educational changes, providing effective teacher feedback, and managing diverse faculty. Mentoring, peer collaboration, and targeted workshops may support sustained and high-quality instructional leadership.

The Schools Division Office may implement the Instructional Leadership Capacity Enhancement Plan to help school heads adapt to changes, provide effective teacher feedback, coach staff, and manage diverse faculty, with follow-up and mentoring to ensure consistent application and measurable improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study complied with accepted ethical guidelines for doing research in education. Prior to data collection, all participants gave their informed consent. Participation was completely optional, and participants were made aware of their freedom to leave the study at any moment without facing any repercussions. All respondents' confidentiality and anonymity were strictly upheld, and all information was gathered, stored, and processed in accordance with relevant data privacy laws. Throughout the research procedure, the respondents' well-being was protected, and no physical, psychological, or emotional harm occurred. The authors affirm that there was no conflict of interest during the study's execution. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly citing and acknowledging sources, and the analysis and interpretation of the results were done impartially and objectively. The study's findings were only utilized for scholarly and investigative purposes. The authors retain full responsibility for the content, analysis, and conclusions; artificial intelligence tools were only used to help with language editing and document structuring.

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